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TENTATIVE IMPEDANCE BUDGET IN THE COLLIDER AND PULSED SYNCHROTRONS

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Abstract:

First impedance models for the chain of four Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons have been developed, investigating the impact of RF cavities and normal conducting magnets vacuum chamber design. For the 10 TeV collider, the vacuum chamber of the arc magnets was studied, using the current magnet radial build. The impedance models stored and shared on a CERN Gitlab repository were then used in tracking simulations to assess the transverse coherent stability limits and find mitigation measures.

MuCol Consortium, 2025

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This report presents initial impedance and beam stability studies for the Muon Collider (MuCol) project, focusing on the Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS) chain and the 10 TeV collider ring.

The four-stage RCS chain accelerates muons from 63 GeV to 5 TeV using superconducting RF cavities. High-order modes (HOMs) from these cavities and the design of vacuum chambers for the pulsed, normal-conducting magnets, contribute significantly to the transverse beam coupling impedance. Tracking simulations show that instabilities can occur but are mitigated with positive chromaticity ($Q' = +20$) and transverse dampers for injection jitters up to $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in each RCS. Further investigations are needed to increase this tolerance to injection errors.

The collider ring uses superconducting magnets with a tungsten liner to protect the magnet from muon decay products. The transverse impedance of a 10 km tungsten vacuum chamber with different copper coatings was evaluated. Tracking simulations then used these results, integrating the muon decay effect as well. Simulations show that chromaticity of $Q' = \pm 2$ with a transverse damper can suppress instabilities for injection jitters up to $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$.

Impedance models and simulation data are available via CERN GitLab and an attached website explaining the model used and providing data visualization tools.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the high-intensity muon and anti-muon bunches are accelerated through the different machines of the Muon Collider, they interact electromagnetically with their surrounding environment, such as the RF cavities or the vacuum chambers. These parasitic electromagnetic interactions are modelled as impedance in frequency domain or wakefields in time domain. Impedance and wakefields can be computed with analytical formulae for some simplified cases or dedicated simulation codes. An impedance model of each machine can then be developed to gather the contributions of different elements.

This model can be used in simulation to model the impact of impedance and wakefield on transverse coherent beam stability. If the muon bunch appears to be unstable, mitigation measures can be added such as chromaticity, a transverse damper and BNS (Balakin, Novokhatski and Smirnov) or Landau damping.

The first impedance and wakefield models developed for the Muon Collider were focused on the high-energy part of the acceleration chain and on the 10 TeV collider ring. For the acceleration chain, four RCS bring the muon and anti-muons bunches from 63 GeV to 5 TeV in a few milliseconds. To achieve this acceleration rate, many RF cavities are required in each RCS. These cavities will have parasitic HOMs that can generate strong short-range and long-range wakefields. Additionally, the design of the vacuum chamber in the pulsed, normal-conducting magnets of the RCS will have to minimize eddy current effects. A ceramic chamber with metallic stripes is proposed, to reduce the beam coupling impedance. In the collider ring, the main impedance driver is the vacuum chamber. A tungsten pipe is used to shield the superconducting magnets from muon decay. The chamber impedance with different copper coating thicknesses was evaluated, and the impact on the transverse coherent beam stability was assessed, including the effect of muon decay.

2. IMPEDANCE AND BEAM STABILITY SIMULATIONS FOR THE RAPID CYCLING SYNCHROTRONS

IMCC and MuCol are studying a 10 TeV greenfield muon collider which comprises a chain of four RCS to accelerate the muon and anti-muon bunches from 63 GeV at the end of the Recirculating Linacs (RLAs) to the 5 TeV for injection in the collider ring [1]. The main parameters of the RCS used for impedance and transverse collective effects studies are listed in Table 1. To meet the muon survival rate target in the high-energy acceleration chain, the RCS require large acceleration gradients, necessitating a high number of RF cavities capable of achieving these gradients. For example, in RCS 1, the energy gain must reach 14.8 GeV per turn to lose only 10% of the intensity to muon decay. To achieve this, around 700 TESLA superconducting RF cavities operating at 1.3 GHz, each with an individual accelerating gradient of 30 MV/m, will be needed. HOMs in these cavities can generate wakefields that, combined with high muon and anti-muon bunch intensities, could disrupt beam motion, leading to emittance blow-up and particle losses. Additionally, the fast ramping of normal conducting magnets in the RCS constrains the vacuum chamber design to minimize eddy current-induced power losses. Ceramic is used as the main material for the chamber, along with an inner metallic RF shielding to reduce impedance effects. An initial radial build of the vacuum chamber is proposed, addressing constraints from magnets, powering, vacuum, and impedance.

Table 1: Main parameters for the RCS accelerator chain used in impedance and stability simulations [1].

Parameter	Unit	RCS 1	RCS 2	RCS 3	RCS 4
Injection energy	GeV	63	314	750	1500
Extraction energy	GeV	314	750	1500	5000
Circumference	m	5990	5990	10700	35000
Acceleration time	ms	0.34	1.10	2.37	6.37
Number of turns	-	17	55	66	55
Energy gain per turn	GeV	14.8	7.9	11.4	63.6
Number of bunches per species	-	1	1	1	1
Inj. bunch population	10^{12}	2.7	2.4	2.2	2
Ext. bunch population	10^{12}	2.4	2.2	2	1.8
Transverse normalized RMS emittance	μm	25	25	25	25
Momentum compaction factor α_p	10^{-4}	24	24	10	10
Longitudinal RMS emittance	eV s	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Max. pulsed dipole field	T	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
Max. steady dipole field	T	-	10	10	16
Ramp rate	T/s	4200	3282	1519	565
Number of cavities	-	700	380	540	3000
Cavity gradient	MV/m	30	30	30	30

2.1. IMPEDANCE MODEL OF THE RF CAVITIES AND THE NORMAL CONDUCTING MAGNETS VACUUM CHAMBERS

The RCS will include many RF cavities to provide the required acceleration gradient to the muon and anti-muon bunches as reported in Table 1. The cavities will generate HOMs whose properties depend on their geometric design. Two types of TESLA cavities were considered: the classic TESLA cavity [2] and the Low-Loss type [3]. Figure 1 shows the transverse dipolar wakefield generated by HOMs in a single TESLA cavity or a Low-Loss cavity. Studies focused on the impact of short-range wakefields (up to 100 ps). In this case it is the R/Q of the HOMs that determine the short-range wakefield strength. Since some of the Q factors for the HOMs were not available in literature, the Q factor of all the modes were set to $Q=10^5$, a typical range for the Q values of HOMs.

Figure 1: Transverse dipolar wakefield generated by the HOMs of a Low-Loss cavity (orange curve) and a classic TESLA cavity (blue curve). The study focused on the short-range wakefield, where Q factors were all set to $Q=10^5$.

For the normal conducting magnet vacuum chambers, a first radial build is proposed to address constraints from magnets, powering, vacuum, and impedance and is pictured in Figure 2. A 5 mm thick ceramic chamber would be used, and an inner RF shielding is needed to ensure beam image current continuity and reduce beam coupling impedance. An impedance of the chamber was developed, scanning different RF shielding thickness. The chamber is approximated as a circular chamber with a uniform inner copper layer. A scan on the shielding thickness was also realised. The transverse dipolar impedance for a one-metre-long chamber was computed using ImpedanceWake2D [4]. Figure 3 shows the resulting impedance for the different copper layer thicknesses. Without shielding, strong resonances appear from the GHz range, but adding a 100 nm metallic coating can attenuate these resonances [5].

Figure 2: Proposed radial build for the RCS normal conducting magnets vacuum chamber. Beam dimensions are for the beams in RCS 1 at injection energy.

Figure 3: Real part of the transverse dipolar impedance for different inner RF shielding thicknesses. Picture from [5].

2.2. IMPACT ON TRANSVERSE COHERENT BEAM DYNAMICS

Macroparticle tracking simulations using Xsuite [6] and PyHEADTAIL [7] evaluated the impact of impedance on single-bunch transverse coherent stability from RCS 1 injection to RCS 4 ejection. The effect of an initial transverse offset of the beam at injection in each ring was also considered. Instability mitigation measures, such as a transverse damper and chromaticity, were investigated [8, 9]. Figure 4 shows an example of the evolution of transverse beam parameters through the chain of four RCS, for an unstable and stable configuration.

Figure 4: Evolution of the transverse beam parameters of a single muon bunch through the chain of four RCS. On the left plot a strong coherent instability appears in RCS 1 after a few turns, leading to emittance blow-up. On the right plot, introducing chromaticity $Q' = +20$ stabilizes the beam, and the transverse emittance is preserved through the chain.

The transverse emittance at the end of the chain was compared to the initial emittance. Figure 5 shows a map of this emittance growth for the different parameters that were scanned. With classic TESLA cavities, simulations found that a positive chromaticity of $Q' = +20$ is required in all four RCS to preserve transverse beam emittance for initial transverse offset resulting from injection jitter up to $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in each RCS [8, 9]. Further studies are required to increase the admissible jitter in each RCS, as injection jitters up to several hundred of micrometres are common for accelerators.

Figure 5: Transverse emittance growth heatmap for the HOMs wakefield of the Low Loss cavity (left plot) and the classic TESLA cavity (right plot), for a range of transverse damper setting (vertical axis) and injection jitter (horizontal axis). Both cases use a chromaticity of $Q' = +20$.

3. IMPEDANCE AND BEAM STABILITY SIMULATIONS FOR THE 10 TEV COLLIDER

The 10 TeV centre-of-mass collider ring of the Muon Collider has two interaction points where the muon and anti-muon bunches collide head-on. The ring would operate at a fixed energy of 5 TeV per beam. As the muon decay over time, decay products must be intercepted to protect the superconducting magnet coils from heating and radiation damage. A tungsten liner would therefore be inserted inside the magnet cold bore. Moreover, the ring would be isochronous, i.e. operating with $\eta=0$ to remove the need for large RF voltage while preserving the short bunch length. The main parameters for the ring are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Main parameters for the impedance and beam stability simulation of the 10 TeV collider.

Parameter	Unit	Collider 10 TeV
Beam energy	GeV	5000
Circumference	m	10000
Number of bunches per species	-	1
Number of interaction points	-	2
Inj. bunch population	10^{12}	1.8
Transverse RMS normalized emittance	μm	25
Slippage factor η	-	0
Longitudinal RMS emittance	eV s	0.025
RMS Bunch length $1\sigma_z$	mm	1.5

3.1. IMPEDANCE MODEL OF THE COLLIDER VACUUM CHAMBER

Over the 10 km long collider ring, the arc magnet vacuum chamber is the main impedance source. Studies focused on the chamber transverse impedance estimation for different radii and materials. The model assumes a 10 km long circular chamber, made of tungsten at 300 K. Given that the tungsten liner has a thickness of at least 3 cm, it is approximated as an infinitely thick layer for impedance studies. A copper coating on the inner side of the chamber is also added to improve electrical conductivity and therefore reduce the strength of the wakefields. Figure 6 shows the current radial build of the magnets, with an inner radius of 23.5 mm. Figure 7 shows the real part of the transverse impedance for a circular chamber of 23 mm diameter, with different copper coating thicknesses, as well as no copper coating. As expected, adding a copper coating to the tungsten liner helps reduce the transverse impedance and with thicker coatings, this reduction is achieved over a larger frequency range.

Figure 6: Proposition for the 10 TeV collider arc magnets radial build. The inner radius of the tungsten shielding serves as the beam vacuum chamber. A copper coating is also present on this inner radius to increase the electrical conductivity. Picture from [1].

Figure 7: Real part of the transverse dipolar impedance of a 10 km long circular chamber for the 10 TeV collider. The different curves show different copper coating thicknesses, from no coating (orange curve) to a 100 μm copper coating (green curve) and is also compared to a case with pure copper (blue curve).

3.2. IMPACT ON TRANSVERSE COHERENT BEAM DYNAMICS

The bunches will decay over time: at 5 TeV, the relativistic gamma factor is $\gamma = 47323$ and therefore the muon half-life in the laboratory frame is $\tau = \ln(2) \gamma \tau_0 = \ln(2) 47323 \cdot 2.2 \mu\text{s} = 72 \text{ ms}$ which corresponds to ~ 2200 turns in the 10 km collider. The bunch-intensity reduction over time helps mitigate coherent bunch instabilities since the muon and anti-muon bunch intensities will quickly decrease. This effect was therefore added to the tracking simulation performed with Xsuite and PyHEADTAIL. Parametric studies were also performed to investigate the effect of an initial beam jitter and check mitigation measures such as chromaticity and a transverse damper. Simulations found that a slightly positive or negative chromaticity, such as $Q' = \pm 2$ is required to stabilize the beam for injection jitters up to $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ [10]. Figure 8 shows two examples of tracking simulation, one with chromaticity at $Q' = 0$ in which case an instability develops, and one with chromaticity $Q' = +2$ in which case the beam remains stable.

Figure 8: Evolution of the horizontal bunch parameters over time in the 10 TeV collider of a single muon bunch. The left plot shows a case with chromaticity corrected to $Q'_x=0$: an instability develops, leading to emittance growth (second topmost plots), despite muon decay that reduces the bunch intensity (bottommost plot showing the particle loss over time). The right plot shows a simulation with chromaticity $Q'_x=+2$: the instability is mitigated, and no emittance growth occurs.

4. AVAILABILITY OF THE IMPEDANCE MODEL AND RELATED DATA

The impedance models for the RCS and the Collider rings are made available on a CERN Gitlab repository at the address <https://gitlab.cern.ch/muon-collider-bd/muc-impedance>.

Documentation pages are also available at the address <https://muc-impedance.docs.cern.ch/>, with the impedance model data presented in interactive plots. The related data can also be downloaded from the pages.

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